

Generative-AI for AI/ML Model Adaptive Retraining in Beyond 5G Networks

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ABSTRACT Beyond fifth-generation (B5G) networks aim to support high data rates, low-latency applications, and massive machine communications. Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) can help to improve B5G network performance and efficiency. However, dynamic service demands of B5G use cases cause AI/ML model performance degradation, resulting in Service Level Agreements (SLA) violations, over- or under-provisioning of resources, etc. Retraining is essential to address the performance degradation of the AI/ML models. Existing threshold and periodic retraining approaches have potential disadvantages, such as SLA violations and inefficient resource utilization for setting a threshold parameter in a dynamic environment. This paper proposes a novel approach that predicts when to retrain AI/ML models using Generative Artificial Intelligence. The proposed predictive approach is evaluated for a Quality of Service Prediction use case on the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) Software Community platform and compared to the predictive approach based on the classifier and a threshold approach. Also, a real-time dataset from the Colosseum testbed is considered to evaluate Network Slicing (NS) use case with the proposed predictive approach. The results show that the proposed predictive approach outperforms both the classifier-based predictive and threshold approaches.

INDEX TERMS AI/ML Model Retraining, Beyond fifth-generation Networks, Generative AI.

I. Introduction

THE Beyond fifth-generation (B5G) networks are bringing transformations in the next-generation networks by supporting a range of use cases such as massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC), ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (uRLLC), and enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB). However, Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) recognizes that there is a strong need for network intelligence to address the complexity of B5G networks effectively and meet the growing service demands. Artificial

Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) techniques offer a promising solution as they can effectively handle complex network architectures and make intelligent decisions (i.e., resource allocation based on the predicted user traffic) [1], [2], which makes them suitable for B5G networks.

Operator Defined Open and Intelligent Radio Access Networks (O-RAN), Telecom Infra Project (TIP), and Open RAN Policy Coalition, and many others are actively working towards enabling the *intelligence* in B5G networks. Here, the O-RAN Alliance architecture enables *intelligence*

through two logical RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs): Non-real time RIC (Non-RT RIC) and Near-real time RIC (Near-RT RIC) [3]. The Non-RT RIC operates use cases with a granularity of at least 1 s, while the Near-RT RIC operates use cases on a timescale between 10 ms and 1 s.

Utilizing AI/ML models enhances the performance of B5G networks, but it comes with several challenges [4]. One significant challenge is maintaining performance consistency with AI/ML model — which is crucial for decision-making in network management use cases. The dynamic changes in incoming user data traffic in B5G networks contribute to model performance degradation, thus impacting AI/ML-based applications [5]. This issue is especially critical, as it can lead to false insights, inaccurate decision-making, and potentially severe service interruptions. Moreover, it results in inefficient resource allocation and utilization [6], where over/under-provisioning can lead to network performance degradation and service disruptions.

The above factors influence the pre-defined SLAs between service providers and users [7]. For example, in an automated guided vehicle (AGV) use case, the SLA defines a predicted throughput of 80 Mbps. However, when an AI/ML model performance degradation occurs, the model may not predict the expected SLA throughput, which leads to violations of pre-defined SLAs [8]. Therefore, addressing the model performance degradation is crucial in B5G.

To ensure the AI/ML model performance — the model retraining (or updating) with newly arrived user data is an effective strategy. In [9], a threshold approach is proposed to trigger model retraining. This approach continuously monitors key performance metrics such as *accuracy*, *precision*, *recall*, or *F1-score* and initiates retraining when these metrics fall below or exceed a pre-defined threshold. [10] triggers retraining whenever the Autoencoder (AE) reconstruction error violates the pre-defined threshold. However, determining the appropriate threshold value poses significant challenges — too low may result in excessive computational costs due to frequent retraining — too high may lead to poor model performance and violate SLAs. In [11], the models are updated at regular intervals regardless of changes in the user traffic or performance of the deployed AI/ML model.

The AI/ML model retraining is predicted (namely predictive approach) by determining changes in user traffic through an unsupervised classifier — Local Outlier Factor (LOF) [12]. This approach minimizes SLA violations and optimizes resource utilization. However, classifier based predictive approach [12] has certain limitations, such as — (i) fails to determine changes in user traffic whenever the changes are not continuous; (ii) may not be suitable for the incoming user traffic with high variance and can lead to frequent retraining; and (iii) the method used to determine the number of consecutive windows (or data chunks) to trigger model retraining might vary depending on the specific application being considered.

To address the limitations of statistical measures within the threshold approach [9], [10] and unsupervised classifiers employed in the predictive approach [12] for AI/ML model retraining, this paper introduces a novel predictive approach by utilizing the capabilities of Generative AI (Gen-AI) [13], [14]. Gen-AI capitalizes advanced features to effectively capture and model the underlying distribution of user traffic, unlike traditional statistical measures that have limitations in handling complex and dynamic data distributions. Gen-AI can adapt to complex user traffic patterns in dynamic environments by enabling the dynamic nature of user behavior within B5G networks.

Gen-AI enables more realistic simulations of diverse network scenarios [15], aiding in predicting AI/ML model retraining to align with evolving user traffic patterns in dynamic B5G environments, thus enhancing predictive capabilities and reducing SLA violations.

Incorporating Gen-AI is significant for mitigating SLA violations and improving computational resource efficiency by generating synthetic data resembling observed traffic patterns.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- A novel approach to predict the AI/ML model retraining using Gen-AI — Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs).
- The proposed predictive approach is evaluated for both the QoS prediction use case over the O-RAN software community (OSC) platform [16] and a real-time slicing dataset from the Colosseum [17].
- Discussion on various challenges and complexities involved in leveraging Gen-AI for B5G networks.

II. Background

Generative AI — VAE and GAN, is a broad category of AI/ML techniques that focus on generating new user traffic data that closely resembles observed (or trained) data. VAEs generate data by capturing the observed data that underlie the distribution and sampling from a learned latent space. On the other hand, GANs use a combination of the *generator* and *discriminator* networks to generate new user traffic data. The *generator* network generates synthetic data, also known as “fake data” or “generated data,” to resemble the distribution of the observed data. Whereas, the *discriminator* network distinguishes between the observed and the generated data.

The detailed descriptions of both VAE and GAN as follows:

A. VAEs

Figure 1 shows the VAE architecture consists of two neural networks: an *encoder* and a *decoder*. The encoder takes user traffic data (i.e., x), and transforms into a latent space representation (i.e., z) — describes the probability distribution of every input value and approximate new user

FIGURE 1. VAE architecture

traffic data [18]. The *encoder* is represented as $q_\phi(z|x)$ and parameterized by ϕ to provide the mean and variance of a *Normal distribution* from which the latent variable z is sampled. The *decoder* is denoted as $p_\theta(x|z)$ and parameterized by θ , takes the latent variable z as input and generates the parameters of the distribution x . The primary objective of the VAE is twofold: (i) to minimize the reconstruction error of the user traffic data; and (ii) to minimize the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence [19] between the observed data distribution $p(z)$ and the newly generated data distribution (i.e., encoder) $q_\phi(z|x)$ as in Equation (1).

$$V(\theta, \phi) = \mathbb{E}_{q_\phi(z|x)} [\log p_\theta(x|z)] - D_{KL}(q_\phi(z|x) || p_\theta(z)) \quad (1)$$

The VAE can generate new user traffic data upon training, where latent variable is $z_i \sim p(z)$ and a new user traffic data sample is $x_i \sim p(x|z)$.

B. GAN

FIGURE 2. GAN architecture.

Figure 2 shows the GAN architecture, which consists of two neural networks: the *generator* and the *discriminator*. In the GAN architecture, adversarial training is employed, where a generator competes with a discriminator to produce realistic data. The GANs have demonstrated in capturing complex distributions and generating user traffic closer to actual traffic [20]. The GANs does not make assumptions about a specific distribution for latent space representation as in VAEs. Thus, the GANs offer increased flexibility in modeling various user traffic patterns.

The generator network takes a random *noise* vector z as input and attempts to create fake data, which resembles the input data traffic during training. In contrast, the discriminator attempts to classify the generated data from the observed data accurately. Loss convergence of the generator and discriminator completes the training period. Essentially, both the generator and discriminator networks are jointly involved

in a 2 – player min-max game, as shown in Equation 2 until the discriminator fails to distinguish between the observed and generated data [21].

$$\min_{\theta_G} \max_{\theta_D} L(G, D) = \min_G \max_D \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{\text{data}}(x)} [\log D(x)] + \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_z(z)} [\log 1 - D(G(z))] \quad (2)$$

Where x is the user input data, p_{data} is the observed data distribution, $p_z(z)$ is the noise distribution, $\log(D(x))$ is the predicted output of the discriminator for x , and $\log(D(G(z)))$ is the output of the discriminator on the GAN generated data $G(z)$. The aim is to maximize the ability of the discriminator to identify observed data from generated data (i.e., \max_D). In contrast, the generator part of the Equation tries to minimize the discriminator's ability to classify observed and generated data correctly (i.e., \min_G).

The applications of Gen-AI in the Radio Access Network (RAN) include generating synthetic data, resource optimization, network planning, and Quality of Service (QoS) management [13], [14], [21]. However, the proposed predictive approach leverages the Gen-AI to determine when to retrain an AI/ML model, which is detailed in the section III

III. System Model and Proposed Approach

This section describes the system model and the proposed approach to predict when to retrain an AI/ML model.

A. System Model

Figure 3 shows the O-RAN architecture in which two RAN RICs are defined: the Near-RT and the Non-RT [3] to employ the *intelligence*. These RICs enable B5G network autonomous optimization by operating at different timescales depending on the position of the AI/ML model inference [22].

The O-RAN architecture provides various interfaces, including O1, A1, and E2, to enable data collection and communication among the RAN components — Central Unit (O-CU), Distributed Unit (O-DU), and Radio Unit (O-RU). The *O1-interface* obtains the user traffic data from all the components (O-CU, O-DU, and O-RU and model deployment/termination information from Non-RT to Near-RT RIC. The *A1-interface* publishes policy-based guidance, AI/ML performance feedback, verification, and monitoring information between Non-RT and Near-RT RIC. The *E2-interface* is to control the RAN functions through E2-control messages.

The Non-RT RIC is part of the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) and facilitates radio resource management and policy optimization within the RAN. Non-RT RIC consists of AI/ML model management to manage data collection, preparation, model training, and deploying AI/ML inference as an x/rApp. Simultaneously, AI/ML continuous operation monitors deployed x/rApp performance and through the A1 interface. The Near-RT RIC module

FIGURE 3. System model.

operates with granularity between 10 *ms* and 1 *s*, enabling near-real-time optimization, control, and data monitoring of O-CU and O-DU nodes. Near-RT RIC components include AI/ML inference in the form of xApp, data collection and preparation to monitor the RAN performance. The details of the proposed approach are in the following section.

B. Proposed Approach

The proposed approach predicts when to retrain the AI/ML model by exploiting Gen-AI — VAEs and GANs — to generate data that are close to the observed and then performs the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS Test) [23] over both the generated and incoming user traffic data to trigger retrain. Here, the KS Test is used to determine whether the incoming user traffic follows the observed data distribution or not. Algorithms 1 and 2 depict the proposed predictive approach implemented using both VAEs and GANs respectively. Table 1 reports the definitions of the parameters/variables that are used.

Algorithm 1 Predicting AI/ML Model Retraining Using VAEs.

```

1: Input:  $ds, \mathcal{D}\mathcal{E}, P_{VAE-kstest}, WS, z$ 
2: Output: Retrain the AI/ML model or not
3: while data_available do
4:   for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $\lfloor \frac{length(ds)}{WS} \rfloor$  do
5:      $gd_{data} \leftarrow \mathcal{D}\mathcal{E}(z)$ 
6:      $P_{value} \leftarrow KST[gd_{data}, ds[i * WS \text{ to } ((i + 1) * WS - 1)]]$ 
7:     if  $P_{value} < P_{VAE-kstest}$  then
8:       Retrain the AI/ML model
9:     end if
10:  end for
11: end while
    
```

Algorithm 1 takes $ds, \mathcal{D}\mathcal{E}, P_{VAE-kstest}, WS$, and a z as inputs and predicts whether to retrain an AI/ML model or not as an output using VAEs. The incoming data stream ds divides into consecutive chunks of data with a length of WS , and the decoder ($\mathcal{D}\mathcal{E}$) takes the latent space z as

input and generates data (i.e., gd_{data}) of length WS (see lines 4-5). The gd_{data} is compared with the data chunks WS from the incoming user traffic using the KS Test to determine changes in the incoming user traffic. The KS Test computes the maximum distance between the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the two distributions (i.e., gd_{data} and ds). Here, KS Test calculates a P_{value} , representing the probability that the ds and the gd_{data} are from the observed data. A lower P_{value} indicates the arrival of significant changes in incoming user traffic. Whenever the P_{value} is lower than $P_{VAE-kstest}$, the proposed approach triggers retraining of the AI/ML model, indicating that the traffic from the incoming user is different from the underlying observed data (see lines 7-10).

Algorithm 2 Predicting AI/ML Model Retraining Using GANs.

```

1: Input:  $ds, D, G, P_{GAN-kstest}, \mathcal{D}_{score}, WS, Noise$ 
2: Output: Retrain the AI/ML model or not
3: while data_available do
4:   for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $\lfloor \frac{length(ds)}{WS} \rfloor$  do
5:      $Y_{predict} \leftarrow D(ds[i * WS \text{ to } ((i + 1) * WS - 1)])$ 
6:     for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $WS$  do
7:       if  $Y_{predict}[j]$  is in  $\mathcal{D}_{score}$  then
8:         Do_Nothing
9:       else
10:        Warning Zone
11:       end if
12:        $z \leftarrow Noise$ 
13:        $gg_{data} \leftarrow G(z)$ 
14:        $P_{value} \leftarrow KST[gg_{data}, ds[i * WS \text{ to } ((i + 1) * WS - 1)]]$ 
15:       if  $P_{value} < P_{GAN-kstest}$  then
16:         Retrain the AI/ML model
17:       end if
18:     end for
19:   end for
20: end while
    
```

TABLE 1. Description of variables used in the algorithms.

Acronym	Referring to / Definition
ds	Incoming data stream
\mathcal{DE}	Decoder neural network architecture of VAE
$P_{VAE-kstest}$	Value determined by Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test (KS Test) between the generated and observed data during the training of VAE
WS	Window Size
$Noise$	A source of variability or randomness injected into the GAN model to generate diverse and realistic data The proposed work employed Gaussian noise throughout the study
z	Samples from the distribution considered in $Noise$
gd_{data}	Generated (or new) data from Decoder \mathcal{DE}
$\mathcal{DE}(z)$	Decoder \mathcal{DE} , taking a vector z_i of size WS as an input, which is sampled from z
KST	KS Test, which quantifies the distance between two distributions based on their empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDF) and determines whether the incoming user traffic follows the observed data distribution or not
P_{value}	Value determined by KS Test for each window of length WS by comparing both generated and incoming user data
D	Discriminator built with multi-layer perceptron neural network to differentiate between the observed and generated data
G	Generator built with the LSTM architecture to generate data close to the observed data
$P_{GAN-kstest}$	Value determined by Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test (KS Test) between the generated and observed data during the training of GAN
\mathcal{D}_{score}	Range of discriminator score (i.e., between 0 and 1) obtained for the observed data during training of GAN
$Y_{predict}$	Stores the D prediction output in a list
gg_{data}	Generated (or new) data from Generator G
$G(z)$	Generator G , taking a vector z_i of size WS as an input, which is sampled from z

Algorithm 2 takes ds , D , G , $P_{GAN-kstest}$, \mathcal{D}_{score} , WS , and a $Noise$ as inputs and predicts whether to retrain an AI/ML model or not as an output using GANs. The Discriminator D predicts whether the incoming user traffic belongs to the observed or not over each data sample in the data chunk (see lines 4-6). The D assigns a score between 0 and 1 for each data sample, and if the score lies in the range of \mathcal{D}_{score} , no action will be taken (see lines 7-8). Otherwise, a $warningzone$ notifies by indicating changes in the incoming user traffic (see lines 9-10), and helps to collect data for model retraining, if required. The generator (G) takes the $Noise$ as input and generates data (i.e., gg_{data}) of length WS (see lines 12-13). The gg_{data} is compared with the data chunks from the incoming user traffic using the KS Test to determine changes in the user traffic. The KS Test is applied on the two distributions (i.e., gg_{data} and ds) and calculates a P_{value} . Whenever the P_{value} is lower than the $P_{GAN-kstest}$, the proposed approach triggers AI/ML model retraining, indicating that the incoming user traffic is different from the underlying observed data (see lines 14-17). During the retraining, the previously trained AI/ML model weights are updated based on the newly available data.

Figure 4 depicts the workflow between the O-RAN modules and the proposed predictive approach, detailed as follows: The AI/ML model management registers model and stores its information into the data repository (1-2); the AI/ML training service module initiates model training by retrieving requested data from the data repository (3-6); once the model training is complete, it will be deployed as xApp using dms_cli tool (7-9); the predicted user traffic through xApp can be stored into the data repository (10); the proposed predictive approach continuously retrieves the in-

coming user traffic data from the data repository and reports to AI/ML model management through AI/ML continues operation upon determining the changes in the user traffic (11-13); the AI/ML model management triggers retraining based on the proposed predictive approach and updated model is deployed using dms_cli tool (15-17).

IV. Evaluation Setup

The proposed predictive approach evaluated for two use cases: (i) *Quality of Service (QoS) prediction* [24] over the O-RAN software community (OSC) platform, and (ii) *Network Slicing (NS)* using a real-time dataset [17]. Description of each use case and its corresponding experimental setup are as follows:

A. QoS Use case

The proposed approach is evaluated for *QoS prediction* use case, which focuses on predicting the service quality (i.e., throughput) provided by network operators to their customers [25], [26]. Figure 5 depicts the experimental setup used to evaluate the QoS prediction use case, in which the proposed approach is deployed at the Non-RT RIC platform and integrated with the OSC RIC platform.

The OSC Near-RT RIC framework (F-release), an E2 simulator, and various open interfaces [16] are utilized within a Kubernetes (K8s) pod. Other OSC components like E2 manager, routing manager, subscription manager, app manager, and shared database (InfluxDB) are deployed as K8s microservices. The Near-RT RIC employs a key performance metric monitoring (KPMON) xApp for monitoring RAN layer statistics, and a QoS prediction (QP) xApp using

FIGURE 4. Proposed Approach Workflow.

a three-layer Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) [27] model for predicting QoS values.

An OSC E2 simulator consists of a 5G core, O-CU, O-DU, and O-RU. The RAN components establish communication with the Near-RT RIC through the E2 control messages such as (1) E2 setup request; (2) E2 setup subscription; and (3) E2 setup indication as shown in Figure 5. In addition, the E2 simulator can be connected with multiple User Equipments (UEs) through a customized JavaScript Object Notation (json) file.

Note that the current F-release of OSC does not include a complete implementation of the SMO and the Non-RT RIC frameworks. Therefore, to evaluate the QoS prediction use case using the proposed approach, the missing functionalities in the OSC platform are implemented and deployed on a bare metal server. For example, the *dms_cli* tool is used to onboard the trained model at the Near-RT RIC as a microservice. Moreover, the proposed predictive approach is implemented as a Representational State Transfer (REST) application programming interface (API) to monitor changes in user traffic by accessing real-time data (i.e., throughput) from the InfluxDB database through a customized API.

The Near-RT RIC and E2 simulator are connected and integrated with the proposed predictive approach — which used a Gen-AI techniques to determine changes in the incoming user traffic and trigger retraining when necessary — deployed in Non-RT RIC to provide AI/ML model management functionalities.

B. Network Slicing Use case

Network Slicing (NS) is a key feature of B5G networks, involves segmenting a single physical network into virtual slices, each tailored to meet the unique demands of specific use cases. The ability to allocate resources, configure parameters, and provide distinct service characteristics for each slice offers flexibility and efficiency. Moreover, enabling NS at the RAN — an interface between UEs and the core network — is important for optimizing resource utilization and ensuring a seamless end-to-end slicing architecture [17].

NS, can vary based on the user traffic demands as the B5G networks continue to evolve and MNO has to adapt to the user demands effectively [7], [28], [29]. MNOs can employ AI/ML models to predict the incoming user traffic through RICs in the form of r/xApps and allocate the resources using RAN controller messages as shown in Figure 6. However, the employed AI/ML models may not perform well as network service demands continue to evolve by introducing a new NS traffic. The proposed approach determines changes in the user traffic and predicts the need for model retraining to support the evolving NS demands.

To evaluate the NS use case with the proposed predictive approach considered a real-time dataset collected from the Colosseum testbed [17]. The dataset is collected from the urban scenario of Rome, Italy, with 4 Next Generation Node Bs (gNBs) and 40 UEs. The locations of the gNBs cover an area of 0.11 km^2 (i.e., square kilometer).

FIGURE 5. QoS experimental setup.

FIGURE 6. Slicing use case [7]

The Colosseum dataset is based on a multi-slice scenario in which UEs are assigned to a slice of the network and request three different traffic types: high-capacity eMBB, uRLLC, and mMTC. The gNBs serves each slice with dedicated scheduling policies. The scenario considered in this dataset concerns pedestrian user mobility with time-varying path loss and channel conditions. Traffic among gNBs and UEs is generated through the Colosseum traffic generator (TGEN), configured to send different traffic types to UEs of different slices such as: (i) eMBB: 1 Mb/s constant bit rate traffic; (ii) uRLLC: Poisson traffic, with 10 pkt/s of 125 bytes; and (iii) mMTC: Poisson traffic, with 30 pkt/s of 125 bytes.

Three scenarios are available based on UEs mobility and the UEs distance from the gNB [17] — Static Close, Static Far, and Slow Close.

The available data sets scenario details are as follows:

- Slow Close — The UEs are uniformly distributed within 20 m of each gNB while moving 3m/s.
- Static Close — The UEs are uniformly distributed within 20 m of each gNB with no mobility.
- Static Far — The UEs are uniformly distributed within 100 m of each gNB with no mobility.

The performance results are obtained for all the above three scenarios and understood the proposed predictive approach is able to perform equally independent of the UE distance and the mobility. Due to the proposed predictive ap-

proach adaptability — GANs and VAEs are capable enough to learn the complex data distributions/patterns.

In this paper, Slow Close is considered for the performance valuation.

C. Performance comparison

The proposed predictive approach is compared with the other two approaches to evaluate the performance. The other two considered approaches are as follows:

- **Threshold Approach [10]:** Triggers the model retraining whenever the considered AI/ML model performance metric exceeds the pre-defined threshold. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) over each data chunk of size WS serves as the performance metric for the threshold approach.
- **Predictive Approach [LOF] [12]:** Predicts when to retrain the AI/ML model by exploiting a LOF classifier that calculates the local density deviation for each incoming user data sample and determines whether it belongs to the observed or new data. If new user data arrive over a certain number of windows of size WS — which can be calculated as a function of the time taken to transmit the considered data samples from the data stream (i.e., T_{ds}) and the end-to-end delay of the application under consideration (i.e., T_{e2e}) — then the predictive approach [LOF] triggers retraining.

The performance of the proposed and considered approaches are evaluated with the following key metrics:

(i) *Model Retrain Trigger Time (MRTT)*: It is defined as the time taken between the occurrence of a change in the user traffic and the AI/ML model triggering for retraining.

A shorter MRTT signifies the efficiency of an approach in promptly identifying changes in incoming user traffic. The MRTT is crucial for assessing how quickly an approach can adapt to dynamic user behavior.

(ii) *Model Re-Placement Time (MRPT)*: It is defined as the time taken to retrain an AI/ML model and to replace with the existing model. A shorter MRPT is essential for minimizing SLA violations and addressing resource utilization issues arising due to the changes in the incoming user traffic.

V. Results

This section presents the results obtained for the use cases under consideration — (i) QoS Prediction and (ii) NS. Additionally, a comparative analysis of the proposed approach with the other two approaches such as (i) Predictive approach [LOF] and (ii) Threshold approach, are presented. Also, the details of GAN, VAE, and LSTM architecture are listed in Table 2.

A. QoS Prediction (QP) Use case

The deployed QP xApp is implemented using the LSTM model and trained with data collected from KPMON xApp and other datasets [17], [30]. Figure 7 depicts the performance of the considered approaches in predicting the throughput. To evaluate the QoS use case, the input parameters for all the considered approaches are as listed in Table 3. Here, the $P_{VAE-kstest}$ and $P_{GAN-kstest}$ values are determined during the training phase. Other parameters like T_{ds} and T_{e2e} are use case specific [8], while WS depends on operator requirement. Here, the larger WS value provides more stability by tolerating short-term changes in

TABLE 2. GAN, VAE, and LSTM model description

GAN	Generator	Architecture	LSTM layer + 3 Fully Connected (FC) layers
		Output Activation	Sigmoid
		Loss Function	Binary Cross-Entropy
		Learning Rate	0.001
	Discriminator	Architecture	3 FC layers
		Output Activation	Sigmoid
		Loss Function	Binary Cross-Entropy
		Learning Rate	0.001
VAE	Encoder	Architecture	Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)
		Latent Dimension	32
		Loss Function	KL Divergence
		Learning Rate	0.001
	Decoder	Architecture	MLP
		Activation function	Sigmoid
		Loss Function	Mean Squared Error (MSE)
		Learning Rate	0.001
LSTM	Architecture	3 LSTM layers with 100 hidden units	
	Activation function	rectified linear unit (ReLU)	
	Loss Function	MSE	
	Learning Rate	0.001	

FIGURE 7. Evaluation of QoS Prediction (QP) xApp.

user traffic, whereas a smaller WS value increases sensitivity to immediate changes in user traffic, allowing for a prompt response but potentially leading to frequent retraining.

TABLE 3. Input parameters list of QoS use case

Approach	Parameter	Value
Threshold Approach	RMSE	15
Predictive Approach [LOF]	T_{ds}	20 ms
	T_{e2e}	5 ms
Proposed Predictive Approach	WS	10
	$P_{VAE-kstest}$	0.00182
	$P_{GAN-kstest}$	0.00206

Figure 7 shows the evaluation of QP xApp as a function of cell throughput. Initially, from 0 ms to 139 ms — pedestrian traffic is considered, and 140 ms onwards multiple UEs with different data rates are configured to create changes in the incoming user traffic (i.e., the bottom plot of Figure 7). In this scenario, the *threshold approach*

FIGURE 8. Performance comparison of the considered approaches.

identified changes in user traffic 270 ms - 280 ms and initiated retraining at 280 ms upon the RMSE exceeded the pre-defined threshold. The retrained (e.g., LSTM) model is replaced at 395 ms for continuous throughput prediction. Whereas, the predictive approach [LOF] triggered retraining at 180 ms after detecting changes in user traffic 140 ms

- 180 ms and replaced at 295 ms . The proposed predictive approach — both GAN and VAE trigger retraining at 150 ms and replaced with a retrained model at 260 ms and 260 ms to predict the throughput values accurately.

FIGURE 9. Sampled PMF of model retraining trigger time.

Figure 8 presents both MRTT and MRPT for each of the considered approaches. The shorter MRTT shows the proposed approach efficiently detects user traffic changes and helps decrease the retraining time due to fewer samples considered for retraining. However, this cannot be identified from the captured results (i.e., MRPT) due to the lower number of samples in all the considered scenarios. Moreover, this could differentiate with larger samples required to be retrained.

Figure 9 shows a sampled Probability Mass Function (PMF) between the time required to identify the occurrence of a change in user traffic (i.e., MRTT) and the frequency of such occurrences. On the Y-axis of occurrences represent the percentage of instances out of 60 (1-hour duration) to trigger retraining after the occurrence of an actual traffic change. Whereas, the X-axis is a discrete variable as the MRTT will be a factor of WS . The threshold approach exhibits a maximum of 25% occurrences at 60 ms , while the predictive approach [LOF] shows approximately 85% occurrences at 40 ms . In contrast, the proposed predictive approach [GAN] and [VAE] achieves approximately 98% occurrences at 10 ms , and 95% occurrences at 10 ms , respectively. Thus, the proposed predictive approach — GAN and VAE — effective determination of user traffic changes.

B. Network Slicing (NS) Use case

Figure 10 shows the considered Slow Close with the considered approaches in predicting downlink tx_brate . The input parameters for all the considered approaches are listed in Table 4

As shown in Figure 10, initially, the eMBB slice traffic is considered and user traffic change is introduced at 500 ms by streaming the mMTC slice traffic from 500 ms onwards. Here, the threshold approach triggers retraining at 590 ms upon detecting changes 500 ms - 590 ms with model

TABLE 4. Input parameters list for NS use case

Approach	Parameter	Value
Threshold Approach	RMSE (eMBB \rightarrow mMTC)	15
	RMSE (mMTC \rightarrow uRLLC)	5
	RMSE (uRLLC \rightarrow eMBB)	15
Predictive Approach [LOF]	T_{ds}	20 ms
	T_{e2e}	5 ms
Proposed Predictive Approach	WS	10
	$P_{VAE-kstest}$ (Slow Close)	0.01235
	$P_{GAN-kstest}$ (Slow Close)	0.01568

replacement at 750 ms . Similarly, the predictive approach [LOF] initiates retraining at 540 ms after detecting changes 500 ms - 540 ms with model replacement at 680 ms . In contrast, the proposed predictive approach using both GAN and VAE triggers retraining at 510 ms after identifying changes in user traffic, with model replacements at 628 ms and 630 ms , respectively.

Furthermore, UEs switches from the mMTC slice to the uRLLC slice, observable from 1000 ms . The threshold approach detects traffic changes 1000 ms - 1060 ms , triggers retraining at 1060 ms when the RMSE surpasses the threshold and the model replacement at 1200 ms . Also, the predictive approach [LOF] triggers retraining at 1040 ms after detecting changes 1000 ms - 1040 ms , with model replacement at 1180 ms . Whereas, the proposed predictive approach using both GAN and VAE starts retraining at 1010 ms upon identifying changes in user traffic, with model replacements at 1125 ms and 1130 ms , respectively, to ensure accurate throughput predictions.

Figure 11 illustrates the MRTT for each of the approaches for the Slow Close scenario based on Figure 10. It can be observed that the MRTT for the proposed predictive approach based on Gen-AI techniques — GAN and VAE is smaller compared to the other approaches, due to the following reasons: (i) Gen-AI techniques are capable enough in adapting to dynamic network conditions, traffic patterns, and user behaviour; (ii) The proposed predictive approach employed the KS Test to determine distribution similarity, which enables the promptly determining user traffic changes.

In the case of the threshold approach, the RMSE values are low during the initial stage of incoming new user traffic, however, in the later stages the RMSE values exceed the predefined thresholds. Thus, the threshold approach always exhibits the higher MRTT when compared to other approaches. As stated earlier, the predictive approach [LOF] operates mainly based on the selected number of windows with size WS , hence the approach must wait for the considered number of windows before triggering the retraining, which leads to the higher MRTT when compared to proposed predictive approaches.

FIGURE 10. Slow_Close - eMBB → mMTC → uRLLC.

FIGURE 11. Slow close

In summary, the proposed predictive approach based on the Gen-AI outperforms the other approaches for use cases such as QoS prediction and NS. The choice of these use cases is driven by their vital role in B5G networks. QoS prediction ensures consistent network performance, while NS is essential to meet the user demands without violating SLAs. Both use cases demonstrate the adaptability and effectiveness of the proposed predictive approach. A performance comparison reveals that the changes in user traffic are effectively

adapted by the proposed predictive approach — Gen-AI compared to the predictive approach [LOF] and the threshold approach.

VI. Complexities and Challenges

This section explains the complexities and challenges of dealing with Gen-AI.

A. Model Complexity

Model complexity involves the number of parameters, features, or rules within Gen-AI techniques to learn from data and make predictions accurately. The complexity of Gen-AI introduces potential difficulties during implementation and integration into the RAN through RICs. Effectively managing Gen-AI complexity requires specialized expertise in deployment and maintenance. Overcoming the challenge of model complexity is essential for ensuring the successful and robust integration of Gen-AI in B5G networks.

B. Model Generalization

Model generalization refers to the capability of a Gen-AI technique to produce meaningful and accurate outputs not

only for the trained data but also for new/unseen data — drawn from a similar distribution. Model generalization emerges as a critical concern in the realm of Gen-AI implementation for B5G networks — when the model has limited generalization, the model may lead to incorrect predictions for new/unseen data. Thus, ensuring these Gen-AI techniques can effectively generalize their learned patterns and behaviors for diverse scenarios/use cases. In B5G networks, Gen-AI models must exhibit a robust ability to adapt and perform consistently well under various conditions. Addressing this challenge is imperative for unlocking the full potential of Gen-AI in contributing to the adaptability and efficiency of B5G networks.

C. Model Interpretation

Model interpretation involves the process of understanding and explaining the outputs and behavior of Gen-AI techniques. Wireless systems need to be engineered with justifiable results and performance guarantees when integrated with different network components and requirements. Unfortunately, most of the existing Gen-AI techniques follow a black-box approach without explaining why and how the approach led to the given outcome. Developing eXplainable AI (XAI) with interpretable and predictable outcomes is one of the key challenges for applying Artificial Intelligence (AI) to B5G networks.

D. Computational Intensity

The proposed predictive approach — Gen-AI outperforms the other approaches, however, note that Gen-AI requires a higher computational cost compared to other approaches. Mitigating the computational overhead is crucial for the adoption of Gen-AI models, particularly when considering deployment at the network edge. Exploring strategies to compress Gen-AI techniques or efficiently distribute the computation becomes imperative to balance performance excellence and resource efficiency in real-time applications.

VII. Conclusions

Beyond 5G (B5G) networks are expected to bring transformations in the next-generation networks by utilizing Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) techniques. However, maintaining performance consistency with the AI/ML model is crucial for different use cases such as massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC), ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (uRLLC), and enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB). In this paper, the proposed predictive approach utilizing Gen-AI — VAE and GAN — to predict the AI/ML model retraining in order to maintain AI/ML model consistency. The proposed predictive approach is evaluated by implementing on the OSC platform and a real-time dataset for two different use cases — *QoS Prediction* and *Network Slicing*. The performance results showed that the proposed predictive approach outperforms the state-of-the-art — predictive approach [LOF] and thresh-

old approach — by detecting user traffic changes promptly after they occur, thus helps in reducing SLA violations significantly. In particular, control loop time (i.e., model retraining trigger time, model retrain and replacement time) reduction in terms of microseconds can be achieved. Based on this study, the potential future directions of this work are as follows: (i) *Exploring the Reinforcement Learning (RL)*: Formulating AI/ML model retraining as a decision problem and investigating RL algorithms for efficient decision-making; and (ii) *Incorporating XAI*: Integrating XAI to enhance model interpretability, providing insights into the reasons behind Gen-AI predictions.

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